

Baseline Report

Multi-Disciplinary Design and Optimisation of Long-Range eVTOL Aircraft

DSE group 06

Student Name	Student Number
Kaizad Wadia	4789849
Jakob Schoser	4843754
Alejandro Montoya Santamaría	4789946
Michael Buszek	4773934
Miguel Cuadrat-Grzybowski	4838726
Egon Beyne	4797957
Nikita Poliakov	4804236
Javier Alba Maestre	4844009
Koen Prud'homme van Reine	4878965
Noah Salvador López	4882512

Tutor: Saullo Giovanni Pereira Castro
Coaches: Davide Biagini and Ali Nokhbatolfoghahai
Institution: Delft University of Technology
Place: Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft
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Executive Summary

Around the world, many cities suffer from increasing traffic and congestion problems. Vertical take-off and landing aircraft are a promising technology to alleviate this problem. Due to their ability to overfly obstacles, move independently of ground infrastructure and take off from anywhere, they could allow for very fast door-to-door transport. It is the aim of this DSE project to explore this market opportunity and design a VTOL aircraft that can carry four passengers over 300 km. Due to the growing relevance of sustainability in transport, the design space will be constrained to electric VTOLs (eVTOL). The mission need statement of the project is as follows:

Provide sustainable, personal aerial transportation for inter-city travel that is competitive with the current transportation methods while requiring minimal infrastructure.

In the report at hand, several aspects of this mission are investigated in detail and the information is used to generate technical requirements. Finally, possible designs for the mission are identified and selected for further analysis.

Chapter 2 outlines the functional analysis of all stages of the project. This is a crucial step in the design, since analysing the functions required by the design process and eVTOL provide a clear picture of the use case. On a high level, the functions were investigated in five phases: mission introduction, aircraft design, production and delivery of the aircraft, operation of the aircraft, and disposal of the aircraft. Aircraft operation is of the greatest interest to the customer, which is why it is analysed in greater detail than the others: the steps taken in pre-flight actions, take-off, cruise, extending the mission, landing and post-flight actions are broken down to up to four levels to capture detail. The result can be seen in the functional flow block diagram and functional breakdown structure.

In Chapter 3, the market opportunities for a long-range eVTOL are explored. Among the possible target industries, the commercial transport and private sector were deemed the most promising. With its range of 300 km, the eVTOL could satisfy the needs of intra-city travel, but most importantly be used for inter-city travel as well. In Europe, 300 km is a typical distance to be covered by commuters and tourists in business and personal trips. It is in this market segment where a long-range eVTOL could hope to gain a lot of traction. Furthermore, it could be a comfortable personal mode of transport for higher income populations. Europe and the United States provide good conditions for this. Europe in particular is suitable since it has many major cities at small distances from each other. Based on previous studies, it was concluded that a market size of 15 billion US dollars could be achieved by 2040 for eVTOLs in the chosen market segment. This corresponds to annual sales of about 5000 units. The team could aim to partake in this with 205 eVTOL vehicles sold per year, priced at 1.5-3 million apiece. The direct competitors would be helicopters and other eVTOL projects.

To inform the sustainable planning of the project, Chapter 4 lays out a literature review on the environmental and social sustainability of eVTOLs. It is found that eVTOLs produce less greenhouse gas emissions than conventional internal combustion engine cars for distances longer than 50 km. Larger distances allow the eVTOL to take advantage of the aerodynamically optimised cruise configuration. However, the sustainability of eVTOLs may be limited by their energy source. Especially Lithium-Ion batteries cause high environmental impact in production and are created from scarce natural resources often obtained from mines with questionable humanitarian standards. Therefore, alternative batteries or hydrogen fuel cells should be considered as alternatives.

Management of the technical risk was done in Chapter 5. Technical risks include risks associated with technical failures of the aircraft, but also errors made during the design. First the main technical risks were identified, and given a score based on the severity of the risk. In total 22 risks were identified.

Using these scores the most severe risks were selected, a total of 9 risks were deemed necessary to manage. These were managed by either reducing the probability of occurrence or the consequence associated with that risk. For most risks this was done by requiring minor design features to be added to the concepts.

In Chapter 6 technical budgets were allocated to the different systems of the aircraft. This can help in the design of the different systems, as the designers have an idea as to how much resources they can use for their system. Budgets were made for weight, cost, thrust, drag and power. Apart from allocating budgets, also the resource contingencies were determined for each design stage. These contingencies represent a margin to the maximum change in budget size for each subsystem. If the contingency is exceeded, either a redesign or a change of the initial budget size should be considered. As can be expected, the contingency margins reduce when the design progresses, as the level of detail increases, and with it the uncertainty in resource usage.

The requirement discovery (documented in Chapter 7) was initiated with the identification of the stakeholders of the project, as well as their needs. The stakeholders identified for the project were the customer, regulatory bodies, citizens, passengers and the pilot. Their needs were compiled into requirements, that were then further used to create system and subsystem requirements. The subsystems investigated were the propulsion, power, control, structure, cabin, and lifting subsystems. From this, 8 key stakeholder requirements and 14 driving requirements were distilled to guide the design.

Finally, Chapter 8 used a design option tree to identify three relevant options for further investigation. Drawings of these concepts are shown below.

Figure 1: Tandem aircraft with distributed propulsion system.

Figure 2: Box wing with distributed propulsion.

Figure 3: Single wing aircraft with 6 engines, 4 rotating.

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1 Introduction

Designing aerospace systems is a complex endeavour with many possible solutions and dependencies between subsystems. This results in a large problem space that is challenging to tackle without a systematic approach. Such an approach is provided by the systems engineering framework. In this report, the crucial first steps for systems engineering are laid out. The aim is to provide a baseline for more detailed analysis of selected concepts in the subsequent design stage.

In Chapter 2, a functional analysis of the project is outlined with a functional flow block diagram (FFBD) and a functional breakdown structure (FBS). Through a detailed market analysis, information for marketing and pricing the eVTOL is presented in Chapter 3. Ideas and strategies to promote environmental and social sustainability in the outcome of the design process can be found in Chapter 4. Chapter 5 highlights the technical risks anticipated in the project and proposes mitigation measures whose impact is also explored. As an initial guideline for design, technical resource budgets and the corresponding contingencies are explored and shown in Chapter 6. All this information is combined in Chapter 7, where the requirements for the project are described. Finally, in Chapter 8, it is explained how the solution space was explored by means of a design option tree, and then reduced to three configurations for closer investigation.

2 Functional Analysis

2.1. Functional Breakdown Structure

In order to provide an overview of the system, and identify the functions it needs to perform, a functional breakdown structure (FBS) was made of the entire aircraft life-cycle, with emphasis on the operation of the aircraft. Later on, these functions can be translated into requirements.

Figure 2.1: Aircraft life-cycle

As can be seen from Figure 2.1, there are five main phases to the aircraft's life. All of them, except for phase 4, are broken down into two levels in Figure 2.2. This gives a general overview of what these phases entail. When it comes to phase 4 - *Operate aircraft*, it has been broken down in 4 levels, with level 4 being included only where deemed necessary. The decision to provide more detail in this phase was due to the fact that this is the longest stage of the life of an aircraft and that the functions of the aircraft itself are showcased.

The breakdown of the *Operate aircraft* focuses specifically on a mission cycle, starting from pre-flight actions and ending on post-flight actions. Additional functions have been included, such as continuous functions of aircraft and dealing with emergency situations. Continuous functions are active throughout the mission and are thus not possible to put in the chronological order. For the same reason, they have been omitted from the Functional Flow Block Diagram in the next section.

2.2. Functional Flow Block Diagram

The functional flow block diagram (FFBD) is useful when it comes to analysing a nominal flight and understanding the chronological order of the functions involved. The number of levels that the FFBD can have is only a limit of the engineer's imagination, however for the sake of efficiency and clarity, the FFBD for *Operate aircraft* displayed is expanded to level 3 only. Although concise, this level provides enough detail in order to gain a deeper understanding of the aircraft's functionality. Other phases are given to level 2, just like in the FBS.

The nominal mission is quite standard for all long range passenger aircraft, with a few deviations with regards to the fact that the aircraft in consideration is a VTOL aircraft. Possible deviations from the nominal mission, like loiter and diversion, are also considered. The reasons for the loiter and diversion are not given, but these are closely related to *Deal with emergencies* column in Figure 2.2. The top level functional flow is simply: *perform pre-flight actions, take-off, cruise, (avoid landing zone), land, perform post-flight actions*, in that order. Nevertheless, each of these top level functions are quite complex and comprise of multiple lower level functions. This reveals another use of the FFBD, to show the breakdown of functions involved. Although this can be considered a redundant function, since the breakdown is already shown in Figure 2.2, it is still a function of it nonetheless. For instance, only FFBD can be shown and not FBS, depending on the nature of the mission.

At times, it happens that functions run in parallel. In such cases, the use of an *AND* connector is made. These are most common in 'child' functions, the 'parent' of which is continuous function, such as cruise. It is also common to see functions that split into several alternative paths. These functions are implemented using an *OR* connector.

Below the functional breakdown structure can be found in Figure 2.2, followed by the functional flow block diagram in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.2: Functional breakdown structure

Figure 2.3: Functional flow block diagram

3 Market Analysis

This chapter deals with a market analysis investigating the feasibility of selling eVTOLs in the market. Section 3.1 lists the potential markets to be explored where eVTOLs could be sold. Then, in Section 3.2, the market share for the proposed eVTOL product is estimated in terms of monetary value and number of units. Section 3.3 details the competitors and challengers present in the eVTOL industry. Due to limited resources, time and manpower, this analysis was constructed through the use of already existing articles and reports from key players in the aerospace industry.

3.1. Target Industries

The very first step of a market analysis for this eVTOL product is to identify all the potential industries where the use and purchase of VTOL units could have a large impact. These include but are not limited to:

- Government and military industry
- Emergency services: police, firefighters, ambulance and natural disaster response officers.
- Commercial Transport.
- Logistics and cargo transport: aerial warehousing and delivery
- Entertainment, leisure and media/
- Construction and building maintenance.
- Private use.

Focus Industries

The team prioritised those industries that are deemed as the most relevant to the type of product to be developed. In this case, the emergence of long range eVTOL aircraft will screen the markets for commercial transport, entertainment and private use. This idea is reinforced by the observed trends during the 2010s decade where the desire and need to adopt Urban Air Mobility (UAM) systems have increased to the point where 1.3 billion US dollars have already been invested in 2021 and is currently rising. [5]

If the product is focused on this industries we can identify a number of stakeholders:

- Passengers: they are the customers of the product
- Pilots: they are needed in order for the mission to be completed
- Citizens: the noise created by the aircraft could disturb citizens.
- Government: They set the regulations that the aircraft has to follow.
- Helicopter manufacturers: the eVTOL is a substitute of the helicopter.
- Public transport: the eVTOL could be a future alternative to trains and buses.
- Car manufacturers: the eVTOL could be a future alternative to travelling by car in order to avoid traffic congestion.
- Energy source provider: whether it is batteries, fuel cells, hydrogen, etc. Success of the eVTOL will result in good marketing for the provider.

One of the main requirements of the eVTOL to be developed by this team defines a maximum range of at least 300 km, which one can attribute to intercity travel when targeting potential travellers. Figure 3.1 illustrates different travel options within UAM mainly differing in the distance to be covered. The eVTOL will be designed to accomplish this 300 km range, but this does not exclude the fact that the same product can be used for intracity and smaller distance travelling; and in the same way, this does not exclude that this team’s eVTOL product can be used outside commercial and private transport.

Figure 3.1: Emergence of a new mobility option. [35]

In 2014, the German-based Institute for Mobility Research (IFMO) published a study in which the current trends and future perspectives of long distance mobility were analysed. Figure 3.2 collects the results of an investigation in current travel demand of German people. It can be observed that a large percentage of both the number of trips and the average travel distance correspond to around 300 km long intercity journeys, which suggests that the implementing this team’s eVTOL product could achieve a high penetration rate in the market segment around commuters, tourists, business and personal trips. It is reasonable to extrapolate this observation to the whole of Europe and European population since Germany is one of the main economies of the European region and German culture strongly influences other central-European countries. Additionally, IFMO state that demographic and spatial development, together with economic evolution and the rise of new technologies are major drivers affecting long distance mobility, increasing the need of more aerial transportation methods. This is supported by a study performed by Airbus in 2019, where it is expected that passenger traffic will grow by 4.3 % and approximately 39 000 new aircraft will be delivered by 2038. [3]

Segment	Number of trips	Average travel distance
Holiday trips (5+ days)	1.0	1,600 km
Short holiday trips (2-4 days)	1.2	410 km
Other personal overnight trips	0.3	410 km
Personal day trips	6.0	200 km
Overnight business trips	1.2	500 km
Business day trips	1.2	150 km
Long-distance everyday personal trips, long-distance commuting and long-distance everyday business trips	5.0	150 km

Figure 3.2: Number of trips per person and average distance travelled per trip.[19]

Therefore, the customers to target are the segment of people living among the largest metropolitan settlements with a potential desire to mobilise through urban, suburban, regional and rural areas. Another lucrative segment include those people with a higher income per capita who wish to spend more attempting to evade today’s urban mobility problems (like traffic congestion and saturated public transport) more comfortably and spanning the same kind of cities.

Market feasibility for such a project can be broken down to consumer demand, operations, infrastructure and timing of all industries involved with aerospace products. Consumer demand itself is driven by the target market, consumer willingness to pay and the availability of the technology used in these products.

All these factors point to the United States and European regions which offer the best possibilities in terms of eVTOL implementation within society. Thus, these two regions would become the main geographical targets to consider and approach.

As a result, the market study performed in this report will exclusively focus on selling eVTOL products within the identified potential markets. The financial and business plans will be built accordingly to ensure success of this promising project.

3.2. Market Calibration

Once the focus industries for this eVTOL product were determined, the team proceeded to estimate the market share that can be achieved by selling eVTOLs in the future. To do so, the market share has to be expressed in both value and number of units.

The race to dominate urban skies has prompted many key players from the aerospace industry to understand the feasibility of developing projects related to Urban Air Mobility. As a result, many market analyses and studies have been recently published by a range of consultancy firms. For example, the firm BIS Research projects that by 2035, the VTOL market will reach 1.9 billion US dollars. [9] On the other hand, NASA hired both McKinsey & Company and Crown Consulting firms constructing parallel analyses. McKinsey believe that market size for Air Taxis (short distance UAM) will reach as high as 500 billion US dollars. [36]. Other studies performed by IDTechEx [24] and Deloitte [16] predict that the global market will rise as much as 14.7 and 17.7 billion US dollars by 2040. Moreover, Reports and Data [42] collected that the market size will reach 7.9 billion US dollars by 2030. While these notorious firms present a significant range in their estimations, one can be certain that the market potential of Urban Air Mobility is only going increase from this point onward and become hugely profitable. Based on these reports, the team has established that the market size for eVTOLs within commercial transport and private use is highly likely to be around 15 billion US dollars by the year 2040.

Next, in order to determine the market size in terms of aircraft unit, the retail price for a single eVTOL must be estimated. To do so, a comparison with direct competitors was carried and explained later in Section 3.3. In essence, the average price of a helicopter was deemed to be 1.8 million US dollars. Early estimations for eVTOL aircraft suggest that the price of a two-seater aircraft will be as high as 1.5 million US dollars, while for its four-seater airliner counterpart can cost up to 3.5 million US dollars. These insights were estimated by Trascend's chief operating officer [43], who also estimated a price of 6 million US dollars for an executive version of an eVTOL aircraft. The price of an eVTOL unit will also depend on the number of units in the series to be produced. Production costs will be reduced as time progresses due to the evolution of necessary infrastructure, evolution in materials with better properties and manufacturing methods. Sale patterns and cost reduction are illustrated in different stages in Figure 3.3. It can be deduced how helicopters currently lie towards the later stages of decline, creating a gap that can be replaced with the emerging market of eVTOLs. Since eVTOLs are still in development and targeting year frames between 2025 and 2040, it is reasonable to suggest that the eVTOL market currently lies the introduction phase and that it will eventually reach the start of the growth phase by 2035. Multiple studies provide evidence of this, where the Compounded Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) is estimated to have a value of 11.1 % between 2021 and 2026 [45] and 13.75 % between the years 2025 and 2035 [9, 8]. Other sources indicate more. As a result, the team forecasts that the initial price for an eVTOL unit can be estimated to lie around 3 million US dollars with the long-term objective of reducing the price down to 1.5 million US dollars.

Therefore, the market size in terms of number of eVTOL units follows from a simple computation dividing the monetary value of the market size by the expected price for a single unit. This yields an estimation of 5 000 eVTOL units to be produced and sold only in 2040.

To explore the market share that could be achieved by this team's eVTOL, the potential regional segments of the focus markets were approached. To do a unit breakdown estimation, the team relied on the current helicopter market where there exist 26 500 civil helicopters worldwide [21] from which a maximum of 15 000 are registered in the US [18]. Nonetheless, KPMG claim that the North American

Figure 3.3: Product Life Cycle [10].

and European markets will have similar size, but emphasise how the Asia-Pacific region will prominently dominate the intracity scene rather than intercity travel [35]. On the other hand, the analysis performed by Markets and Markets [33, 34], it is claimed that Asia-Pacific will have the largest and fastest growing eVTOL market by 2030, where major players like Chinese company Ehang are set to take large market shares. Again, the first reports over regions like Singapore, Japan or even the Middle East seem to indicate these regions' preference of intracity mobility rather than intracity travelling.

Figure 3.4: eVTOL aircraft market size by region (USD million). [33]

As a result, the team crafted a regional market breakdown, with estimations based on the region's readiness to adopt necessary infrastructure, legislation and regulation, in combination with the presence of large potential markets. The estimations are collected in Table 3.1:

Due to the extensive competition and the threat of important players, one cannot expect to achieve a large market share over the entire globe. Instead, the team has set regional targets to capitalize on the foreseen market opportunities. As a result, the team aims to achieve a medium market share of 8 % in Europe which translates in 140 eVTOLs production and sale rate per year in 2040 and a low 2 % market share, or 60 eVTOL units, for North America and Asia-Pacific. The team also expects to take a market share of % 2 for the rest of the world whose markets have not been prioritised, therefore selling an additional 5 aircraft. In total, the team should achieve producing and selling around 205 eVTOL units per year in 2040 (again shown in Table 3.1, excluding those units effectively sold to be used outside commercial and personal transport. The team deems appropriate to focus on Europe during the early

Table 3.1: eVTOL 2040 market breakdown and sales expectation per region.

Region	% Market size	Projected Total Number of Aircraft	Expected Number of Sales
NA	30	1500	30
EU	35	1750	140
Asia-Pacific	30	1500	30
Rest of World	5	250	5

stages of production for a number of reasons, including the upcoming European Union climate-neutral policies and legislation together with the increasing number of manufacturing bases for these advanced aircraft. On the other hand, the team believes that expanding to the North American and Asia-Pacific markets should be done slowly and is to be tackled on a second stage after a solid core of sales in Europe. The team anticipates that selling some units in these markets will help with branding, but shall not be high enough as to hinder production capabilities. Other markets like the Chinese are very prone to set up their own firms with solutions similar to existing products, as observed within computer, vehicle, aircraft and other high-tech industries.

205 eVTOL units per year seems to be a feasible objective, based on a report for the design of a eVTOL, which claims that producing below 450 units is not economically feasible due to the high RDT&E costs per aircraft [26]. The team aims to produce and sell 205 eVTOLs only in 2040, meaning that a much higher number will be produced and sold over the entire project lifespan. For example, assuming a total production of 1000 eVTOLs over a 5 year span yields a value of 200 eVTOL units, which is very close to the 205 units estimated based on the suggested market shares.

Figure 3.5: European map with 300 km radii circumferences around selected cities.

This should be achievable by crafting a financial plan in which the team first focuses on selling in Europe and then expands to the rest of the world. To verify this, the team compared how eVTOL travelling

would perform against other intercity means of transport. It is estimated that by 2040, 42 pairs of North American cities will run eVTOL routes [22]. Figure 3.5 illustrates 300 km radii circumferences around selected major European cities, from which it can be clearly observed that most major cities can be connected with direct eVTOL flights or through a connection in a secondary city. It is an example of how wide can this type of aircraft cover long mobility needs while offering a decrease in traffic congestion, traffic accidents, transport time, pollution and reducing the strain in already existing public transport networks.

It is also worth noting that from figure 3.5 it can be noticed that by increasing the range by 50 or 100 km the travel options could be significantly expanded, for instance, Paris - London, Lyon- Milan and Madrid-Bilbao would be possible. Due to this it is expected that the number of customers when increasing the range would also increase, and thus the market share and the number of units sold of the team would increase. It must also be added that as shown in 3.8 no eVTOL has a range above 300 km, hence all customer that want to travel over 300 km with an eVTOL would have to get this project's aircraft. To estimate the increase in units produced and market size we can use the increase in covered area. If we assume that cities and therefore population are spread homogenously, the number of trips available by increasing the range can be assumed to increase proportionally to the area covered by the eVTOL, which is proportional to the range squared. Assuming the evenly spread population would not be a valid assumption for smaller scales, since the population density is greater near city centers, however, in scales above 50 km this is no longer significant [14]. Based on this principle the number of customers for the eVTOL would increase 36 % for a 50 km increase and 78 % for a 100 km increase. This would mean selling 279 units or 365 units for 50 and 100 km increases respectively in 2040 instead of the predicted 205. However, in reality, the product would become more expensive and customers could choose to use a different travel method, or perhaps to break the trip in two halves which would lower this increase in market size.

This transit network would only become a reality with the governmental support to develop the necessary infrastructure. The concept of vertiports has gained strength lately in the scene thanks to its characteristics. A vertiport is designed to act as a modular hub for eVTOLs. Its design offers flexibility and takes much less space than an airport facility. Its price ranges from 1.5 million US dollars for a small 2-parking vertiport to 15 million for a larger 8-spot vertiport. Vertiports offer numerous important advantages over regular airports, such as the amount of space used and a lower cost per traveller. Figure 3.6 illustrates Lilium's vision for a vertiport after announcing its partnership with the Munich and Nuremberg airports.

As a final step of the market calibration a SWOT analysis was conducted to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the project focusing on the market. The different aspects presented in figure 3.7 should be taken into account when estimating market share, production rate and pricing. Looking into the internal strengths and weaknesses, the issues revolve about the fact that the team is made of students, which has pros, such as no labor cost, and cons, such as the lack of experience. On the other hand, the external opportunities and threats focus on the sustainability aspect of the eVTOL market, and how it can help in the marketing and could provide subsidies. However, there are also threats, which mainly reside on the competition from large companies such as Airbus or Uber.

3.3. Competition analysis

The competition for the eVTOL aircraft being developed can be divided into two main categories, direct, and indirect competition. Indirect competitors are any type of method that can transport people from one city to another, regardless of the method. This would include trains, buses, commercial transport aircraft, cars, boats, etc. More of this type of competition could appear in the future with new technologies such as the Hyperloop. However, the method of accomplishing the transportation differs largely from the method for a eVTOL. The main characteristics that separate these aircraft from the previously mentioned methods are that eVTOLs offer personal transportation, and that they transport through the air. Given this, the currently existing direct competitors for eVTOLs are business jets, and mainly helicopters. Helicopters also share with eVTOLs the capacity of landing and taking off vertically,

Figure 3.6: Lillium's vision for a vertiport. A: Take-off and landing pad. B: Parking spot. C: Terminal. [30]

and also a more similar range and speed. The common range of values for these parameters are shown in Table 3.2 below and compared to the parameters given in the project description. Thus helicopters are the most direct competitors for eVTOLs.

Table 3.2: Comparison of payload speed and range for helicopters, business jets and the eVTOL project [2, 25]

Vehicle Type	Number of passengers	Typical Range	Typical Cruise Speed
Small business jets	6-8	2800-4600	800
Helicopters	4-11	460-650	240
eVTOL project	4	300	100-300

Two helicopter models which can be considered to have very similar missions to the eVTOL and thus are direct substitutes are the Robinson R44 and the Airbus H125. These vehicles can both carry 4 passengers at approximately 240 km/h for distances of 450 and 540 km respectively [2, 11]. It must be noticed that despite the eVTOL having a clearly inferior range, there are 3 main factors that give advantages to eVTOLs and have to be taken into account when determining the pricing [29].

1. Since eVTOLs use electric motors and have multiple rotors for propulsion, their noise level is estimated to be a fourth of what a current helicopter produces. This is positive both for the people living nearby the helicopters trajectory and for the passengers, who will have a more comfortable flight.
2. The electric motors eliminate the complex rotation mechanism and fuel system, which should simplify the structure of the VTOL. This should reduce the maintenance costs significantly.
3. The eVTOL will most likely be safer than a typical helicopter. Firstly, helicopters are difficult to maneuver, which can induce potentially catastrophic pilot errors. Furthermore, because the lift and thrust is produced by a single rotor, failure of this rotor will surely result in catastrophic failure. eVTOLs can be equipped with multiple rotors, such that the other rotors can compensate in case one fails.

However, the competitors within the eVTOL industry must also be analysed. All the investigated eVTOL concepts are still in development, and most of them do not give the estimated price. However other relevant performance parameters such as the speed, number of passengers, and range were available. These are plotted in figure 3.8 below. The name of each of the eVTOLs is presented:

Figure 3.7: SWOT analysis for the project regarding market competitiveness.

Figure 3.8: Graphs presenting the range, cruise speed, number of passengers, and price for selected eVTOL aircraft in the development phase [7, 31, 1, 12, 26].

Table 3.3: The investigated eVTOLs and their corresponding number ID.

Number	eVTOL Project Name
1	Joby S-4
2	Jaunt Journey
3	Archer Aviation
4	VoloCity
5	Lilium 1
6	The Cora
7	CityAirbus
8	EH216
9	VA-1X
10	CityHawk
11	Lilium 2
12	Spricho
13	Duckcampus
14	Mistral Air Taxi

It can be observed that at 300 km, this eVTOL project would match the highest available range out of all of these options, which is achieved by the Lilium jet. Thus it could also be recommendable to further increase the range in order to have the highest range out of all the eVTOL options. Regarding speed, it can be observed that most of the eVTOLs with high range also have a high speed, thus the speed of the eVTOL should also be in the range of 300 km/h in order to be competitive with the rest of the VTOLs. A customer will most likely prefer the option that is fastest in order to reduce the travel time, thus the eVTOL cannot be significantly slower than the competition. Furthermore, it is also important that it is significantly faster than indirect competitors such as trains or cars. For a number of different possible routes in Switzerland and the west coast of the US Lilium estimated that their routes would be between 4 and 8 times faster in all cases than trains or cars, which suggests that improving travel times compared to traditional travelling methods should not be an issue[32]. Regarding price, the estimation for the 3 eVTOL projects, different methods have been applied and differ greatly, and none of the concepts have been put into production. This implies that the accuracy of the values is not verified.

4 Sustainability Plan

Recall the mission need statement of the eVTOL DSE project: "Provide sustainable, personal aerial transportation for inter-city travel that is competitive with the current transportation methods while requiring minimal infrastructure." In order to fulfil this mission, sustainability needs to be considered from an early design stage. This is not only to be understood as sustainability in operation, but rather over the whole life cycle, i.e., considering the phases preceding and following operation. This chapter presents a brief literature review into the sustainability aspects of eVTOLs. It will mainly concern itself with environmental and social sustainability. The third, economic pillar of sustainability is only briefly addressed, since Chapter 3 already establishes the knowledge needed for an economically viable project.

4.1. Environmental Sustainability

There have been multiple studies about the opportunities of eVTOL vehicles as a means of sustainable transport. Kasliwal et al. [28] found that they emit less greenhouse gases per passenger kilometer

than internal combustion engine vehicles for ranges higher than 50 km (assuming the grid carbon intensity of the US). The advantage of eVTOLs increases with larger ranges, since a longer mission implies that a smaller fraction of the time is spent in the power-intensive vertical flight phases. For the performance optimisation of this mission, this means that the time until transition into horizontal cruise flight should be minimised. Other sustainability advantages of eVTOLs are the inherent efficiency of electric powertrains, the ability to take the most direct route between two points even in difficult terrain, and not being affected by traffic, which is an ever-increasing problem in many urban areas. A sensitivity study concluded that the lift-to-drag ratio, grid carbon intensity and to a lesser extent battery specific energy had a strong influence on the global warming potential from a 100 km mission. This highlights design directions to be taken in the further development of the concepts (apart from grid carbon intensity, which cannot be directly influenced by the project but is likely to improve until the product release).

André and Hajek [4] performed a similar study, investigating the climate impacts of three specific eVTOL designs. They made more conservative assumptions with respect to a variety of parameters (including grid carbon intensity) and also considered the environmental impact of production. This led to the conclusion that eVTOLs can only become more sustainable than ground transport in case of little hover time, a very lightweight design and/or a very green electrical grid. Furthermore, the study found that the impact of production (without battery) is generally an order of magnitude less than the impact of operation. End-of-life impacts, in turn, are about an order of magnitude less than production. This clearly shows the priorities to be adopted in the design of the project: when considering climate impact, efficient operation should generally be chosen over the most environmentally friendly production and recycling techniques. While some bio-degradable materials would benefit recyclability, their lower specific properties could still lead to a net increase in greenhouse gas emissions. However, the authors emphasise that battery production is still a very significant contributor to environmental impact for battery-driven designs. Case in point, for every kWh of energy produced by a battery, a third of the emissions can be attributed to battery production.

Therefore, the choice of energy source can be identified as an important factor in the sustainability of the vehicle. Among the different battery types considered by Melo et al. [37] in their life-cycle analysis of eVTOL vehicles, LSB-Li batteries place a smaller burden on the environment than other chemistries. However, the sustainability of all Lithium-Ion based batteries is constrained by the limited availability of the raw materials needed to manufacture them. Lithium, Nickel and Cobalt are in growing demand and need to be recycled in order to allow for a sustainable, circular economy [38]. Recycled batteries also have a lower production greenhouse impact [38] which can be beneficial for the sustainability of the eVTOL project as a whole. While a circular economy for Lithium-Ion batteries is still underdeveloped, many initiatives such as the European Battery directive are pushing for further research and action. In the further development of the eVTOL project, the benefits of near-future battery recycling technologies will be investigated. Furthermore, near-future battery recycling will inform the power related design decisions.

4.2. Social Sustainability

Batteries (if chosen as the energy carrier for the vehicle) could also be a determining factor in the social sustainability of the eVTOL project. According to Mossali et al. [38], cobalt for battery production is almost exclusively obtained from the Democratic Republic of Congo, which has been under scrutiny for human rights violations. To act in a social sustainable way, the eVTOL project should ensure that its supply chain fosters the security and rights of the population rather than further undermining it. Therefore, alternatives to current Lithium-Ion batteries should be considered. For example, Barke et al. [6] suggest that Lithium-sulfur can provide not only for a more environmentally friendly, but also more socially sustainable alternative to Lithium-Ion batteries. A study by Hoque et al. [23] on sustainable energy sources for transport in Western Australia concluded that hydrogen-powered fuel cells would perform better than batteries in terms of social and environmental sustainability, albeit with the drawback that economic sustainability is more uncertain due to the current cost of hydrogen. With increasing demand and infrastructure in the future, however, it could be envisioned that this disadvantage decreases.

Being socially sustainable has more implications in the work environment as well. That is why in the context of design, a human resources director is appointed and actively monitors the well-being of other members of the group. Also, there are several requirements pertaining to the social sustainability of the operations of the vehicle (e.g., taking into account citizens on the ground).

4.3. Economic Sustainability

In order to ensure that the project is economically sustainable in the long term, the product must address a market need that will grow in the future. As explained in Chapter 3, the eVTOL market size in 2040 will probably be around 15 billion US dollars, which provides ample opportunity for the project to establish itself. Electric VTOLs will be desirable to enable faster door-to-door travel times, and can also be a part of the restructuring of urban transport. There is a growing public interest in reducing the number of private cars, and eVTOLs could provide a solution for this scenario. [44] Furthermore, since eVTOLs are not dependent on fossil fuels, their market growth will not be inhibited by their increasing scarcity. However, the depletion of other resources (especially for battery manufacturing) may affect eVTOLs, so this must be considered in the design process.

4.4. Implications for the Design and Trade-off Process

Due to environmental sustainability concerns, multiple requirements were added to the system. No greenhouse gases (except for potentially water), or air polluting substances shall be emitted during operation (VTOL-ENV-1, VTOL-ENV-2). Furthermore, a constraint will be placed on the energy consumption per kilometer and kilogram of payload (VTOL-ENV-3). This is because the energy consumption is generally directly proportional to the environmental impact. Recyclable materials will be considered for the structure, but due to the greater impact of operation compared to production and end-of-life, more importance will be given to operation efficiency. A particular parameter that will be paid attention to is the fraction of the mission spent in vertical flight mode. Being the most power-hungry phase and the main thing that holds eVTOLs back in competing with ground vehicles in terms of emissions, it is important that the time spent in this phase be minimised.

There will be no requirement concerning social sustainability, which can only be evaluated at a later stage in the design when more about the energy source and production methods of the eVTOL is known. Economic sustainability requirements are covered by requirements on efficient ground operation (VTOL-EFG), operational life (VTOL-OPL), and cost (VTOL-COS).

In order to ensure that environmental sustainability goals are met, the chief systems engineer will monitor the energy and power budgets (and requirements). The financial managers will ensure that the product fills the intended market gap and remains within cost constraints. The sustainability officer will check that these functions are fulfilled properly, and additionally bring up issues of social sustainability.

5 Technical Risk Management

Technical risk is a part of every system and subsystem. In order to deliver a successful design, it is not enough to simply use the latest design technologies, but also make sure that all the important risks are identified and managed.

5.1. Risk Identification & Assessment

In this section, the most relevant technical risks associated with the aircraft design are identified. A short explanation is given as to why a risk is relevant, and a score is given based on the likelihood and consequence of each risk. The scale used to determine the scoring is given in Table 5.1 and Table 5.2 for the probability of occurrence and the consequence, respectively.

Table 5.1: Score associated with probability of occurrence.
Obtained from [20]

Score	% Probability	Chance
1	$p < 1\%$	very low
2	$1\% \leq p < 30\%$	low
3	$30\% \leq p < 50\%$	medium
4	$50\% \leq p < 70\%$	high
5	$p \geq 70\%$	very high

Table 5.2: Score associated with consequence of the risk.

Score	Probability
1	Negligible impact
2	Small performance reduction
3	Moderate performance reduction
4	Partial mission failure
5	Complete mission failure

It is important to mention that, where relevant, the risks are considered for the entire life-time of the aircraft and not just a single flight mission.

RT.1 - Calculation errors: During design it is possible that errors are made during calculations. If these are not noticed, wrong results may be used in subsequent steps. The likelihood of calculation errors is very high, depending on the sensitivity of the models used the consequence can be high as well.

RT.2 - Not meeting range requirement: It is possible that during the testing of the aircraft it does not meet the range requirement of 300 [km]. This could occur due to approximations during the design phase, as these accumulate over time. Although the probability of this is not high provided a good design, it could still occur. The consequence of this risk occurring depends on the customer, since some may still be satisfied and some may be totally dissatisfied.

RT.3 - Not meeting lift-to-weight ratio requirement: When an insufficiently powerful lifting mechanism is used, or when the weight is too high, the aircraft might not meet the lift-to-weight (LTW) requirement set. Depending on how far from the requirement it is, the consequence can be a small reduction in performance, or a total mission failure, if the LTW is lower than 1. The probability of this happening can vary somewhat, with a small reduction in LTW being more probable than a larger one. However use of proper design tools and models should ensure a low probability.

RT.4 - Power failure: Power failure involves the failure of the power system, meaning that all the subsystems dependent on electrical power supply shut off. This could happen due to multiple reasons, most common being short-circuits, damage to cabling infrastructure or simple malfunction. This situation is not common but is quite severe. In what stage of the flight the power failure occurs is a big factor, as if the power fails during flight, then the risk is increased dramatically.

RT.5 - Engine failure during cruise: Engine failure during cruise involves both failure due to internal and external factors. Internal factors could be such as malfunction of the propulsion system or any mechanical failure of the propulsion system. External factors would be factors like environmental damage, i.e. hail, birds, dust/sand etc. Once again, having an engine fail entirely is rare but puts the aircraft and its payload, including the passengers, under extreme danger if not mitigated correctly.

RT.6 - Cabin fire: A fire in the cabin can occur due to a host of reasons, the most likely being a short circuit, or a battery fire. Although the probability of this can be considered low, the consequences can be very high, leading to a loss of life.

RT.7 - Engine failure during vertical flight/hover: If vertical flight is mainly performed on engine power, an engine failure could have serious consequences. When a relatively low number of engines

is used, a failure could lead to a crash. If multiple engines are used, the aircraft could still perform a controlled descent, although the probability of an engine failing would be higher. This risk is thus somewhat dependent on the aircraft configuration.

RT.8 - Damage during maintenance/ground operation: This risk is self-explanatory, it simply entails accidental damage occurring during maintenance or ground operation. Unfortunately, the severity of these types of risks varies greatly. The aircraft could sustain a paint scratch, but could also be critically damaged due to a collision with any sort of ground machinery. The probability of this is, unfortunately, hard to predict, but with the current maintenance regulations it is safe to assume it to be low.

RT.9 - Failing certification: Failing certification typically occurs after an aircraft has already been fully designed. This primarily occurs due to design errors or bad management and control. If the certification is not passed, the aircraft cannot use the respective airspace legally, which can be considered a mission failure. However, most often certification fails due to a particular criteria, which then can be easily redesigned.

RT.10 - Unexpected centre of gravity shift during flight: If cargo is not secured properly, or passengers start moving around, the centre of gravity of the aircraft can move during flight. Depending on the seating and cargo arrangement, this could make the aircraft unstable or uncontrollable. The probability of a shift in cg during flight can be considered high. The consequence can be severe, but also negligible. This is largely dependent on the aircraft configuration, and should be re-analyzed once a more detailed concept is developed.

RT.11 - Flutter before reaching maximum speed: Most aircraft experience flutter when reaching certain high speeds. The main risk here is the occurrence of flutter before reaching the never exceed speed (V_{NE}). Proper documentation of the speed of flutter onset at different altitudes should reduce the probability of premature flutter to a low level. If it does occur, the consequences can be high, leading to a damaged aircraft, or even a crash.

RT.12 - Running out of energy during flight: Although an unlikely scenario, due to the nature of the vehicle and heavy dependence on electrical energy, this risk has to be considered. This risk could occur due to pilot error or due to the malfunction of the energy storage system (i.e. battery or fuel cell). The consequence of this is of high concern and such situation should definitely be considered as an emergency situation.

RT.13 - Lightning strike: Even though lightning strikes are a rare occurrence, the consequences can be severe if no precautions are taken. The high voltage can lead to a power failure in the aircraft or damage the aircraft structure.

RT.14 - Control failure: Failure of the control system can occur for both mechanical and electrical control systems, albeit for different reasons. If the system completely jams, the consequence can be catastrophic, depending on the flight phase. Even a partial failure of a rod or a servo can impair the pilot's ability to control the aircraft, and lead to dangerous situations. Most modern aircraft have redundant control systems, such that the probability of a failure remains low.

RT.15 - Hard landing: Crashworthiness is something that all aircraft should consider and is heavily regulated. Although it is unlikely that the aircraft catastrophically crashes, the outcome of this could be detrimental to passenger lives if not designed for properly. On the other hand, hard landings are quite common due to weather changes and therefore have to be considered during structural design to minimise any potential damage.

RT.16 - Maximum load factor exceeded: Either due to pilot errors, or due to weather the maximum load factor of the aircraft can be exceeded. If appropriate safety factors were applied during design, a slight exceeding should not have any consequence, apart from the need of an extra inspection of the airframe. If the maximum load factor is exceeded by a large amount, the consequence is more severe, and structural damage may occur. This could lead to either expensive repairs, or even a crash.

RT.17 - Unacceptable noise level: This risk is not considered for all aircraft, but due to the primary

purpose of the aircraft being to provide comfortable transportation means to the passengers in heavily populated environments, this risk is important. It could again arise from improper design of the aerodynamic and propulsion system, or even improper structural design. Although not life-threatening, failing to comply with noise regulations could deem the aircraft illegal to fly, and thus this risk should be considered.

RT.18 - Aircraft too difficult to control: When stability and controllability of the aircraft were not designed properly, or if errors are present in the control system, the aircraft may be difficult or even impossible to control. Due to the use of simulations and other analysis tools, the probability of this is low. The consequences can be moderate however, leading to difficulties in certification, or in an increased accident rate.

RT.19 - Pilot incapacity: Since the aircraft will be controlled by one pilot only, an important risk to consider is the incapacity of the pilot. If the pilot would be completely unable to fly the aircraft, the consequence can be severe, leading to a crash. Although the probability of a total incapacity is not very high, it is likely that at some point the pilot's flying capability may at least be partially impaired.

RT.20 - Bird strike: A bird strike is not a common occurrence but could be quite severe depending on what damage has been sustained by the aircraft. It also highly depends on the region of operation.

RT.21 - Engine/wing actuator jammed: Mechanical failures such as this are quite common, but most of the time are fixable. The reasons for such a malfunction could be factors like poor design, improper maintenance, or some kind of damage sustained by the mechanical system. The consequence of this could be critical for the mission. The probability is again is hard to predict but is possible to estimate from statistical data, as the issue arises in almost all types of aircraft.

RT.22 - OEW too high: Due to poor design choices, the operative empty weight of the aircraft may exceed the estimated weight. This could lead to a reduction in performance. This is not likely to happen, as accurate tools exist to estimate the weight of the aircraft before building it. Also the consequence may be limited, as the OEW will likely not exceed the estimation by a lot.

RT.23 - Aircraft price is too high: If too expensive materials or manufacturing methods were used, the price per aircraft may be too high. This could also be caused by a long and costly design and development process. Even if the aircraft performs better than its competition, a price that is too high may limit its attractiveness. Since the aircraft will likely use similar materials and thus production processes as its competitors, this is unlikely to cause an increase in cost. Also the preliminary design phase is essentially done for free, leading to a cost reduction. The chances of a prohibitively expensive aircraft are thus low. The consequence can be moderate, as it might lead to lower sales.

RT.24 - Aircraft operations are unsustainable: This risk involves operations themselves but also the infrastructure revolved around the aircraft. Most of the sustainability factors are closely monitored by the regulatory bodies. If the aircraft is deemed unsustainable, it may not be permitted to fly, which would be quite detrimental to the mission. Again, this risk may be caused by many factors. For instance, expensive infrastructure, using unsustainable materials for maintenance or using electrical energy that has been extracted by unsustainable means, like fossil fuels. Luckily, most of the operation sustainability is ensured during the design phase, like making aircraft compact and ensuring eco-friendly maintenance practices.

RT.25 - Operating cost too high: A high operating cost may be caused by the need for frequent repairs, or due to expensive fuels. Since electric engines generally need less maintenance than combustion engines, this will lead to a reduction in operating cost. On the other hand, batteries may need frequent replacement when a high number of charging cycles are performed. If instead hydrogen fuel cells are used, an increase in operating cost may be observed as well. Since the infrastructure needed to produce and distribute hydrogen is not yet enrolled on a large scale, a high operating cost may result. The probability of this is small, but the consequence can be considerable, as customers might opt for more affordable alternatives.

RT.26 - Aircraft less performant than competition: Due to poor design decisions or other flaws

during the design phase, the aircraft may perform not as well as expected. This may be either because the speed is too low, the turnaround time is too long, etc. It could also happen that even though the aircraft does perform as required, it is still outperformed by competitors. The probability of this risk can be considered medium, as competitors have access to the same technologies, but may have more resources to spend on optimizing their designs. The consequence is influenced by the pricing of the aircraft, if the aircraft is relatively cheap, it could still fill a more affordable market segment, leading to a moderate consequence. If the aircraft is in the same price range, the consequence is more severe, as it will likely not sell well.

RT.27 - Aircraft fails to attract customers: It is possible that the end product simply fails to attract customers. This could happen due to various reasons, the most common ones being poor marketing, lack of functionality, high prices (touched upon in RT.23), high competition (already touched upon in RT.26) or an unappealing design. This does not necessarily jeopardise the mission, but will put strain on the company and possibly lead to the project being defunct. The probability of this is quite low considering that the aircraft is targeted at people with high income and that functionality and visual appeal are being considered during the design phase too. This could be a partial failure as then the "competitive" aspect of the mission statement is not satisfied.

RT.28 - Depletion of natural resources: With a growing market for electric vehicles, some resources needed for the production of batteries may become more scarce or at least increase in price. Some of these resources are only found in a few places in the world. This could have an impact on the production cost and thus the revenue from the aircraft. The consequence of this is estimated to be moderate. However, the high demand may also lead to the development of better recycling technologies, alternative chemistries or the discovery of new deposits. Therefore, the probability that this will cause a problem is low.

5.2. Risk Analysis

Below is the table with all risks and their respective score, with the scores explained in the previous section.

Table 5.3: Scoring designated to each risk

Risk (RT)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Probability score	5	2	2	2	3	1	3	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	4
Consequence score	3	4	3	5	3	5	4	4	4	2	5	5	4	5	2

Risk (RT)	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
Probability score	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	1
Consequence score	3	2	4	5	3	4	4	3	3	4	3	4	3

The risks are depicted on a risk map - Figure 5.1. Subsequently, the more critical risks end up in the top right corner. The risks in the red and dark red zones have to be managed, which is done in Section 5.3.

Figure 5.1: Risk map for the technical risks

5.3. Risk Prevention and Mitigation

The most severe risks in Figure 5.1 may endanger the mission. Therefore, these have to be either prevented by reducing their likelihood, or mitigated by reducing their impact. In this section prevention strategies, contingency plans or a combination of both are given for the most severe risks.

RT.1 - Calculation errors

Prevention The probability of serious calculation errors can be reduced by performing a simple sanity check at the end of each calculation. i.e. using engineering judgement to see if results make sense. When calculations are automated, the scripts will have to be verified to confirm their correct implementation.

Contingency plan When a calculation error has been found in earlier work, the only option is to redo all the earlier parts. Automating as much of the calculations as possible can severely reduce the time needed to redo calculations. Not however that the automated calculations themselves will need to be verified as well.

RT.2 - Not meeting range requirement

Prevention To prevent the aircraft from not meeting the high level requirement on range, accurate performance models will have to be used during the design phase. Enough time should also be spent on obtaining correct data to use as an input for these models. To ensure the correctness of the models, either already validated models will need to be used, or new models should be validated before using them.

Contingency plan If it would become clear during a late design stage, or during the flight test phase of the project that the aircraft does not meet the range requirement, either a redesign will be needed, or the reduced range will have to be accepted. This depends on how far the actual range differs from the initial requirement. If the range is still sufficiently high for the aircraft, it is not worth putting more resources into a redesign. If this is not the case, a redesign will be needed if resources allow. If not, the aircraft might fit in a different market segment.

RT.4 - Power failure

Prevention To prevent power failure, or at least prevent it during the flight, the power system has to be checked before every take-off. A thorough check of the power system should be conducted every 6-12 months at least. Practicing conservative power usage will also prolong the lifetime of the system, this involves eliminating any unnecessary power usage.

Contingency plan Once the power has failed, there must always be a back up power system that will ensure aircraft's safe landing. Then the faulty power system could either be replaced or repaired. The switch from the failed power system to the back up one should ideally be instantaneous.

RT.5 - Engine failure during cruise

Prevention To reduce the likelihood an engine failure during cruise, redundancy could be build into the engines by either using multiple engines for one shaft, or by using redundant windings. Also an engine check will have to be performed before each flight. A more thorough inspection should be performed every 6-12 months, to be able to discover underlying issues early on.

Contingency plan If an engine does fail during cruise, the consequences can be minimised by using multiple engines. The more engines are used, the less effect there will be if one fails, since each only provides a fraction of the total thrust.

RT.7 - Engine failure during vertical flight/hover:

Prevention Performing an engine check before every flight should reduce the probability of the engine failure occurring during vertical flight or hover flight. As for the power system, a thorough technical check should be conducted every 6-12 months, since a simple check is not always enough. Having multiple engines on one shaft and having multiple windings in one engine adds redundancy, which decreases the chance of engine failure.

Contingency plan If the failure does occur, the propulsion system must be designed in such a way that the remaining engines should at least be able to slowly descend the aircraft back to ground, while remaining stable and controllable. Such situation should also be introduced in pilot training.

RT.11 - Flutter before reaching maximum speed

Prevention To prevent premature flutter, the speed at which flutter starts can be increased by the structural design of the wing.

Contingency plan Since mistakes can be made during design, in a flight test campaign the complete flight envelope can be tested, and reduced should flutter occur before the design maximum speed.

RT.15 - Hard landing

Prevention A hard landing can be made less likely by putting enough effort into pilot training. Also making the aircraft easy to fly can reduce the likelihood of a hard landing, also having the aircraft intervene automatically when the vertical speed is to high can help to avoid a hard landing.

Contingency plan To reduce the consequence of a hard landing, a lot of focus has to go to crashworthiness during the structural design. For instance, the landing gears and the fuselage itself should be able to withstand hard impact, by introducing dampeners. The cabin seats should provide shock proofing too.

RT.18 - Aircraft too difficult to control

Prevention To prevent the aircraft from being too hard to control, special attention should be paid to the design of the control system. This can be made easier by making designing the aircraft to be stable naturally.

Contingency plan If the aircraft proves to be difficult to fly, small tabs can be placed either in front or aft of the centre of gravity, to either make it more or less stable. This requires relatively few resources, and could even be retrofitted on existing aircraft.

RT.21 - Engine/wing actuator jammed

Prevention The mechanical components of control surfaces, wings and engines should be checked before every take-off. A thorough check is conducted, again, every 6-12 months in order to further lower the risk of such occurrence.

Contingency plan If the actuators get jammed during flight, this should not be detrimental to the mission, the aircraft must divert to another landing zone and safely land and repairs must be made. Pilot must be familiar with such situations from training.

RT.25 - Operating cost is too high

Prevention Designing for low cost operation during the aircraft's life time is the best way to prevent this risk. This involves ensuring easy reparability, maintenance and minimal infrastructure requirement.

Contingency plan In case operating costs are concluded to be high, they have to reevaluated. The manufacturer should devise and provide efficient operation practises to the operators through short-term training. Needless to say, contingency for this type of situation is very cost dependent and prevention should be the main focus.

Revised risk map

In order to document how the practices listed above affect the risks, Table 5.4 has been made. The colour coded columns signify the risks that have been changed with regards to the original Table 5.3. These are again plotted on a risk map depicted in Figure 5.2. From the graph, it is clearly visible that all the risks are now below the red line and thus are of acceptable danger level.

Figure 5.2: Risk map with the most severe risks mitigated

Table 5.4: Scoring designated to each risk

Risk (RT)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Probability score	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
Consequence score	2	3	3	4	2	5	3	4	4	2	5	5	4	5	1

Risk (RT)	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
Probability score	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1
Consequence score	3	2	3	5	3	4	4	3	3	4	3	4	3

6 Technical Resource Budgets

Technical budgeting refers to allocating the available resources among the components of the various aircraft systems. This can be useful during design, as the designers working on a certain system know how much resources they are allowed to use. This way they don't have to consult continuously with the designers of other systems to see if constraints on resources are still fulfilled. This is further described in Section 6.1. As can be expected, some variation in resource allocation may occur during the design, which can influence the budgeting. The allowed variations in budget size are described in Section 6.2.

6.1. Resource Budgets

A technical resource is a technical parameter that drives the design and engineering of a system. The process of allocating these technical resources among the aircraft's various systems and subsystems is called technical budgeting, and it is used to establish a cap on the costs related to those technical resources. The team crafted a resource budget breakdown for this eVTOL product through the use of Philips technical budgeting methods. [39]

The process begins with the determination of Critical to Quality parameters (CtQs), which for an eVTOL, are identified as its mass, thrust, electrical energy and power, drag and economic costs due to their heavy influence in the design process. The crafted table for the technical budgeting is displayed in Table 6.1. Even though the project is in a very early development phase, the budgets displayed below are constructed as part of the preliminary design and trace general guidelines of how the eVTOL product should be finalised. However, the lack of existing eVTOL products combined with the number and differences between concepts generated later in Chapter 8 implies that the generated budgets will be subjected to changes as development progresses in a detailed fashion.

Firstly, the mass budgets use the detailed design of another eVTOL whereby the subsystems were also grouped in a slightly different manner. Through this, it was possible to estimate the percentages by grouping the subsystems as shown in the table below.

The reason behind combining the lift and thrust subsystems is because for the case of VTOLs, the lines between them is blurred depending on the flight condition. The weight and cost budgets has been modelled through statistical similarities between existing eVTOL projects and subsystem components respectively [40, 26, 12, 1]. Engine thrust was allocated entirely to the propulsion system, which will be distributed between thrust and lift depending on the selected concept. On the other hand, a drag estimation cannot be made until a concept is selected due to its large dependency in the aircraft's shape and not the system's properties. Power and Energy were estimated with the help of the code titled Implementation of Chauhan and Martins 2020 [13] eVTOL model by Saullo G. P. Castro. The power during the critical points ($T \approx mg$) was computed as a fraction of the maximum ($T = 1.7mg$). Thereafter the control subsystem was assumed to use minimal power compared to other subsystems, which

Table 6.1: Technical Resource Budgeting for eVTOL

Subsystem	Mass/Weight	Cost	Thrust	Drag	Power	Energy
Thrust/Lift	25%	30%	100%	TBD	80%	60%
Cabin	10%	10%	0%	TBD	15%	35%
Performance	1%	10%	0%	TBD	0%	0%
Control	5%	10%	0%	TBD	5%	5%
Structures	29%	20%	0%	TBD	0%	0%
Power	30%	20%	0%	TBD	0%	0%
Requirement	3175 kg	6 000 000 USD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD

obtained a value of 5% (the lowest increment). This deductively left 15% for the use of passengers in the cabin and other control systems. Using these results, a rough approximation of energy could be used, by taking the weighted average of the power and distance (for a range of 300 km at an altitude of 320 m, a little above a standard set by Uber [41]). A similar process lead to the energy consumption estimate of the control and cabin subsystems. All subsystems that axiomatically do not use a particular resource were not included in the corresponding analysis.

6.2. Resource Contingency Evolution

During the design of an aircraft, estimation are made for the size of the different technical budgets. Because no fixed aircraft exists yet, these budgets can change in the course of the design. To allow for these changes, contingencies are estimated for each budget at a certain design stage. The purpose of these is to give an idea as to how much a budget may change during a certain design stage. If at the end of a design stage the budget is outside of the contingency margin, then the design needs to be revised. If it proves impossible to meet the contingency margin, it might be necessary to change the initial target value [17]. Note that the highest variation was allowed in drag. This is because eVTOLs are new and unconventional aircraft, for which reliable drag estimation methods have not yet been developed. Towards the final design the contingency margins decrease, although some variation was still allowed.

As there is more awareness for the uncertainties present for the detailed (final) design, that is completed first, a 10% (or 20% for drag) margin is included as that is required for critical flight systems. Thereafter, it is possible to work backwards in accordance with the following diagram. This is conducted using the information elucidated in section 20.3 of the book *Concurrent Engineering in the 21st Century* [15].

Figure 6.1: How cost and knowledge are interrelated [15]

This curve describing the evolution of knowledge can be approximated using a parametric mathematical model, described with the following equation (shown in Figure 6.1 by the dotted blue line).

$$\text{Knowledge} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-0.005(9 \cdot \text{time} - 600)}} - 0.005 \quad (6.1)$$

Time and knowledge in the above equation is given in the percentage of the design time (10 weeks) and percentage of complexity accounted for. As during the end of the design process, the full phenomena will still not be known, this will account for 80% of the knowledge. It can be seen in Figure 6.1 that the ease of change decreases as knowledge increases, indicating a more final design. As the margin is used to compensate for the lack of knowledge present, the margin is estimated to be approximately proportional to the relative lack of knowledge. This is formulated using the equation below. Note that a contingency factor of 1.25 corresponds to a 25% margin.

$$\text{Contingency Factor} \propto \text{Lack of Knowledge} + 1 = 1 - \text{Knowledge} + 1 \Rightarrow 2 - \text{Knowledge} \quad (6.2)$$

Through this proportionality and values for the final design it is possible to determine those for the earlier stages. The final margins are based on values from a NASA guideline on contingency management in aerospace systems [27]. They suggest a margin of 15% on structural mass at the stage when "analytical/experimental proof of concept through breadboard validation in relevant environment" has been achieved. This is the furthest the DSE could hope to reach, so this margin is taken on for mass and used as a basis for the other margins as well. The final margin for cost and drag are increased to 20%, since they are more difficult to predict.

Therefore for those with final margins of 10% the midterm margin is $(2 - 0.32) \cdot 1.1/1.2 = 1.54 \approx 1.5 \Rightarrow 50\%$ and preliminary margin, $(2 - 0.11) \cdot 1.1/1.2 = 1.7325 \approx 1.7 \Rightarrow 70\%$. For Drag this is simpler, as it has a final margin of 20% with midterm being $2 - 0.32 \approx 1.7 \Rightarrow 70\%$ and Preliminary $2 - 0.11 \approx 1.9 \Rightarrow 90\%$. All of these results are displayed in Table 6.2.

Table 6.2: Evolution of contingency for the different budgets of the aircraft

Design Maturity	Mass/Weight	Cost	Thrust	Drag	Power	Energy
Preliminary	80%	90%	80%	90%	70%	70%
Midterm	60%	70%	60%	70%	50%	50%
Final	15%	20%	15%	20%	10%	10%

7 Requirements

This chapter elaborates on the process followed to obtain the requirements for the product.

7.1. Stakeholders

Each of these stakeholders has a set of needs that can be found in Section 7.2. These needs have been transformed into stakeholder requirements, which can be seen in the same tree and in Section 7.3. One exception for this is the need of the customers to have an aircraft with low purchase and operating costs. While this will be taken into account in the design and the costs will be minimised, there is no strict requirement on costs for this project. This is justified by the fact that there is no equivalent competitor on the market right now. The closest competitors, as found in Chapter 3, have different weaknesses which this vehicle aims to cover. Hence, if the final product exceeds the offerings from its competitors, having a higher price, within reasonable limits, can be justified. This, together with the fact that due to the lack of comparable vehicles on the market an accurate estimate for the price is not

easy to find, leads to the decision of implementing "Reducing costs" as a design direction rather than a requirement.

7.2. Requirement Discovery Tree

The process of obtaining the requirements started with identifying the needs of the stakeholders, from which stakeholder requirements were derived. This can be seen in the top part of the Requirements Discovery Tree. Secondly, the technical functions and constraints were identified in a second tree. The stakeholder requirements were then placed in this tree. From these requirements, system and subsystem requirements followed. In some cases, there were functions and constraints not covered by the stakeholder requirements, in which system requirements were derived directly from the functions, included in the same tree. Further explanation on each of the categories, as well as on the IDs of the requirements, can be found in the following sections.

Figure 7.1: Requirement Discovery Tree (RDT) for the eVTOL mission

7.3. Stakeholder Requirements

The stakeholder requirements are hereby declared:

- **VTOL-STK-01:** The aircraft shall be able to carry 4 passengers.
- **VTOL-STK-02:** The aircraft shall have a range of 300 km.
- **VTOL-STK-03:** The aircraft shall be able to cover a 300 km trip in within 1 and 3 hours.
- **VTOL-STK-04:** The aircraft shall be able to take off vertically.
- **VTOL-STK-05:** The aircraft shall be able to land vertically.
- **VTOL-STK-06:** The aircraft shall have a ground turnaround time of at most 120% that of its main competitors.
- **VTOL-STK-07:** The aircraft shall be piloted by only 1 pilot.
- **VTOL-STK-08:** The aircraft shall have an operational life of 15 years.
- **VTOL-STK-09:** The aircraft shall have an individual cost below \$6 million.
- **VTOL-STK-10:** The aircraft shall comply with the EASA Proposed Means of Compliance with the Special Condition VTOL ¹.
- **VTOL-STK-11:** The aircraft shall comply with ICAO Annex 16 noise regulations.
- **VTOL-STK-12:** The aircraft shall not emit any polluting substances during operation.
- **VTOL-STK-13:** The aircraft shall be manned.
- **VTOL-STK-14:** The aircraft shall have a cruise altitude above 305 metres.
- **VTOL-STK-15:** The aircraft shall not release any debris to the environment during operation.
- **VTOL-STK-16:** The cabin temperature shall be within 15 and 27 degrees during operation.
- **VTOL-STK-17:** The pressure inside the cabin shall be equivalent to that of being at a height of 2.5 km or less.
- **VTOL-STK-18:** The noise inside the cabin shall be below 84 dBA.
- **VTOL-STK-19:** The seat pitch shall be at least 30 inches.
- **VTOL-STK-20:** The seat width shall be at least 17 inches.
- **VTOL-STK-21:** The aircraft shall have acceptable handling qualities according to MOC VTOL.2135.
- **VTOL-STK-22:** The aircraft shall be stable.
- **VTOL-STK-23:** The aircraft shall have an autopilot system.

7.4. System Requirements

In order to find system requirements the required functions of the system must be defined.

A system requirement follows directly from a function or a system characteristic, the stakeholder name is defined with the function name abbreviation resulting in the following ID convention: **VTOL-FUNC-NUM**. Where VTOL is the mission name abbreviation, FUNC is the function name abbreviation and NUM is the number of the system requirement.

These functions are related to what the system must be able to do, and in this specific case, the system must be able to fly, propel itself forward, with a sufficient amount of energy and it must not break at any time of the mission. This results in technical performance functions which are *Provide thrust (THR)*, *Provide structural support (STS)*, *Resist vibrations (VIB)*, *Provide lift (LFT)*, *Carry payload (PLD)*, *Allow for convenient maintenance (MTN)*, *Allow for convenient ground operation (GND)*, and *Achieve flight performance (PRF)*, *Pilot control (CTL)*, and *Machine flight assistance (MFA)*.

Finally, the system must also allow for other non-technical aspects related to its mission, these are functions and aspects related to the system's constrained performance which are *Safety (SAF)*, *Mass (MAS)*, *Efficient Ground Operation (EFG)*, *Operational Life (OPL)*, *Costs (COS)*, *Social Sustainability (SOC)*, *Environmental Sustainability (ENV)* and *EASA regulations (EAS)*, *ICAO noise regulations (NOI)* and *Crew (CRE)*.

¹https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/proposed_moc_sc_vtol_issue_1.pdf [cited 6 May 2021]

7.5. Subsystems

Before being able to derive subsystem requirements it is essential to define the various subsystems that compose the aircraft system. These are derived from the various functional aspects that the system must provide in order to ensure the success of the mission. These are described as follows with their respective abbreviations.

- **Propulsion subsystem (PRP)** allows the aircraft to be propelled forward by providing thrust.
- **Power subsystem (POW)** stores and provides energy to the entire system in order to accomplish its mission.
- **Control subsystem (CTR)** provides manned and unmanned control over the system. It also ensures that the system is stable.
- **Structure subsystem (STR)** allows the system to be a coherent system. It also provides support and protection to the different subsystem.
- **Cabin subsystem (CAB)** refers to the subsystem that includes payload and furniture and ensures their protection. This subsystem is usually highly associated to the fuselage structure.
- **Lifting subsystem (LIF)** allows the aircraft to be propelled upward by providing a propelling upward force such as lift or thrust.

Having defined and described the subsystems, it is now essential to present the ID convention for a subsystem requirement. These will be written following the convention that was established for the system requirements, with the addition of the subsystem name abbreviation and its dedicated number. The subsystem requirements can be seen in Section 7.2.

7.6. Explanation

A specific number of requirements were established in order to ease in the design process, the ground operations or even to allow for a sufficiently comfortable aircraft for passengers. First, the requirement VTOL-MAS-1 is established for the VTOL aircraft to be certified under a specific category which would simplify the certification process. Secondly, VTOL-PLD-2 refers to VTOL-STK-04, where a standard mass of 95 kg is taken for a passenger, leading to 380 kg of payload for the aircraft system. Thirdly, the acceleration requirements during take-off and landing establish a maximum acceleration for the vehicle, specifically focusing on the comfort of passengers when during take-off and landing. Furthermore, VTOL-MTN-2 allows the aircraft to have a replaceable propulsion system which in turn facilitates inspection and maintenance of the aircraft. Finally, the last requirements are associated to specific ground operations and allow for convenient operations specifically during landing with the first one where the aircraft should be able to land on a vertiport and the second, where the size limit allows the aircraft to be stored during inactivity and/or maintenance.

7.7. Verification strategy

Having explained the rationale of specific requirements, it is now essential to define the different verification methods that will be used to verify requirements.

The first one is inspection. This verification method refers to a more visual procedure that verifies the product geometry or in association with the documentation that the system and checks if it complies with the previously mentioned requirement. The second type of verification procedure is testing. It is defined as a representative model that checks the system's compliance to requirements under specific conditions. This leads to the third method which is demonstration. This establishes by operation or reconsideration of a test article that it complies with requirements. Finally, there is analysis which creates mathematical or analytical techniques which are used to verify the product's compliance with requirements.

The verification method, for each requirement, must be identified and can be seen below:

- VTOL-THR-01: Analysis & Testing
- All of Structure requirements: Testing
- All VTOL-VIB: Testing
- Provide VTOL-LFT-1 to 5 & 7: Testing
- VTOL-LFT-6: Demonstration
- VTOL-LFT-8: Demonstration
- VTOL-PLD-1: Inspection
- VTOL-PLD-2: Testing
- VTOL-PLD-3: Inspection
- VTOL-PLD-4: Testing
- VTOL-PLD-5: Inspection VTOL-PLD-6: Inspection
- VTOL-MTN-1: Inspection
- VTOL-MTN-2: Demonstration
- VTOL-MTN-3: Demonstration
- VTOL-GND-1: Inspection
- VTOL-GND-2: Inspection
- VTOL-GND-3: Demonstration
- VTOL-PRF-1: Testing/Demonstration
- VTOL-PRF-2: Demonstration
- VTOL-PRF-3: Testing
- VTOL-PRF-4: Testing
- VTOL-PRF-5: Testing
- VTOL-PRF-6: Testing
- VTOL-PRF-7: Analysis/Testing
- VTOL-PRF-7-POW-1: Testing/Analysis
- VTOL-PRF-7-PRP-1: Testing/Analysis
- VTOL-CTL-1 &-CTL-1-CTR-1: Inspection
- VTOL-CTL-2: Demonstration
- VTOL-CTL-3 & 4: Demonstration
- VTOL-CTL-4-CTR-1 & 2: Analysis
- VTOL-MFA-1: Inspection
- VTOL-MFA-2: Analysis/Demonstration
- VTOL-MFA-2-CTR-1:Analysis
- VTOL-MFA-3: Demonstration
- VTOL-MFA-3-1 & 2: Testing
- VTOL-MFA-4: Demonstration
- VTOL-MFA-5: Demonstration
- VTOL-MFA-6: Demonstration
- VTOL-MFA-7: Testing
- VTOL-SAF-1: Inspection
- VTOL-SAF-2: Demonstration
- VTOL-SAF-3: Demonstration
- VTOL-SAF-4: Demonstration
- VTOL-SAF-5: Analysis
- VTOL-SAF-6 and -POW-1: Insp
- VTOL-EFG-1 & -POW-1: Demon

- VTOL-OPL-1: Inspection
- VTOL-OPL-2: Demonstration
- VTOL-COS-1 to 4: Analysis
- VTOL-SOC-1: Inspection
- VTOL-ENV-1 & 2: Testing/Analysis
- VTOL-ENV-3: Testing
- All EASA requirements: Testing
- VTOL-NOI-1 & -LIF-1 & -PRP-1: Testing
- VTOL-CRE-1: Demonstration

7.8. Key, Killer and Driving Requirements

First, it is essential to define what key and driving requirements are. Key requirements are requirements that are important to the customer, whereas driving requirements are requirements that drive the design of the system more than average. On the other hand, killer requirements are requirements that bring the design to an unacceptable extent.

The first category addressed during the screening of the requirements was killer requirements. From this process, none of the requirements has been identified as a killer requirement. As the team is still not in the design phase, it is possible that at later stages some requirements that have not been identified yet as such become killer requirements.

Secondly, the key requirements were identified. These can be found in the following list, together with an explanation for this classification.

- **VTOL-STK-01:** This requirement was demanded by the customer and will also be a driving requirement as it will affect the shape and size of the system, specifically where the payload must be carried and protected.
- **VTOL-STK-02 and VTOL-STK-03:** The range and endurance requirements are demanded by the customer and as the previous requirement it is also a driving requirement as it brings limitations in the given design options.
- **VTOL-STK-04 and VTOL-STK-05:** These requirements are key and driving requirements as they define the type of aircraft that the customer wants and also limits and constraints the design to specific types of conceptual designs.
- **VTOL-STK-07:** The aircraft being piloted by one man is demanded by the customer which makes it a key requirement.
- **VTOL-STK-08:** The latter explanation also can be referred to this requirement.
- **VTOL-STK-12:** This requirement is not only required by the customer but also limits the aircraft design and power options which in turn affect most of its internal subsystems. It can be concluded that it is a key and driving requirement.

Lastly, the driving requirements were identified. The following list contains these requirements together with an explanation for the classification.

- **SYS-CU01-01:** The payload of the aircraft will be one of the focal points of the design, which basically sizes the aircraft as a whole.
- **SYS-CU05-03:** This requirement will drive the design in the sense that the aircraft shall be able to both land precisely in a small surface such as a helipad, and also be able to use available infrastructure for helicopters for take off and landing operations.
- **SYS-OPS-04 and -05:** These two requirements drive the size of the aircraft for ground operation. They are driving requirements in the sense that they will heavily constrain the external dimensions of the aircraft due to infrastructure reasons.

- **PRF-SYS-01:** The operational ceiling of the aircraft is a driving requirement since it will have a considerable impact on the lift, thrust and power subsystems so that the aircraft can reach that ceiling. Moreover, if the ceiling is high enough, the aircraft cabin might require pressurisation, which also heavily drives the structures subsystem.
- **VTOL-STK-22 and VTOL-STK-23:** Due to the nature of VTOL aircraft, open loop stability might be unachievable, especially during vertical flight. This requires a control system that provides closed loop stability to make the handling qualities safe and manageable for the pilot.
- **VTOL-STK-10 and VTOL-STK-11:** These regulations need to be met in order to certify the aircraft, hence the vehicle needs to be designed to comply with them.
- **VTOL-STK-13:** Unmanned civil aircraft for passenger transportation will probably not be certifiable in the short- and medium-term future. Thus, in order to ensure that the aircraft is certifiable and ready for the market as soon as possible, making it manned is of uttermost importance.
- **VTOL-STK-14:** This requirement stems from different reasons, which include safety, obstacle avoidance and noise reduction on the ground. All in all, the operating altitude of the vehicle lays a big role in the design of the aircraft.
- **VTOL-MAS-1** A limit on the mass of the vehicle is a hard constraint that will have a big impact on the design of the vehicle.
- **VTOL-SAF-4 and 6:** These requirements impose redundancy on the system, which is an important design consideration that will lead to specific design choices.

8 Design Options

8.1. Design Option Tree

The design option tree is a set of tree diagrams showcasing all design possibilities for multiple design decisions spanning several subsystems. The decisions that are involved in this process are explained in the following paragraphs.

One of the decisions that affects the overall design of the aircraft the most is the choice of the wing configuration. The main focus is on single wing and double wing configurations because of our competitors choices, but wingless aircraft and those with three or more wings were also considered for completeness. The categories are further split into the locations of the wings relative to each other and the type of tail used.

The second decision that contributes greatly to the outside appearance of the aircraft is the propulsion system. Again looking at the competition, mainly propulsion systems using aerodynamic thrust are considered. The main focus was put on different arrangements of rotors, including both jets and open propellers, although more advanced technology is also presented. It must be noticed that this is only for cruise, not for the entire mission. A separate take off tree is also available. The reason for this division is that if it was combined in one tree it would assume that the same designs can be used for take off and cruise, which is not true. For instance, an aerostatic balloon can not be used for cruise.

Another important decision to make is the energy source for propulsion. The most probable energy source is chemical, with a dilemma between combustion, fuel cells and electric batteries. Solar cells might also be a good possibility, mainly as an additional source. Energy storage options from other industries, like nuclear or mechanical, are also considered.

Having described the previous two options, a relevant decision must be made on controllability which also affects safety. For the latter there are many possibilities of equal apparent feasibility. The first control method for airplanes is a control surface like elevators, ailerons and rudders but those are only useful when they can generate sufficient aerodynamics forces, which in turn requires sufficient air velocity. A VTOL aircraft is more demanding when it comes to control, because it also needs to

be controllable during zero-air-speed hovering for takeoffs and landings. Due to these circumstances, mechanical control systems or thrust vectoring techniques might be required to stabilise and control the aircraft.

The aircraft should be able to move on the ground, which is the major driver for the landing gear design. Although conventional helicopters are stuck on the ground after landing, the eVTOL competition is usually able to drive on wheels. Having airplane-like landing gear is also beneficial for safety and crash-worthiness, since a gliding landing on a road or small airfield after engine failure is much safer and more controllable on wheels than it is when sliding on the bottom of the fuselage.

Furthermore, the cabin configuration is greatly related to the shape of the fuselage. Many different arrangements of 5 seats are considered, taking into consideration how to incorporate a streamlined fuselage which can accommodate the previously mentioned seats.

The last subsystem left to discuss is the one used for taking-off and landing. The take-off tree includes a vertical version of the thrust subsystem for the cruise propulsion system and other alternatives that could be only be used for taking-off. However, these alternatives are not for sustained horizontal flight, like aerostatic or mechanical take-off systems. The second stage of flight for an eVTOL aircraft is transitioning from vertical to horizontal flight and hence transitioning to their respective configuration which is done in mid-air. In this tree a multitude of options seem comparably feasible. The entire aircraft or just the propulsion system could be rotated, or a vertical thrust system could be gradually reduced while a horizontal thrust system is gradually implemented.

A combination of all the described design option trees leads to seemingly infinite design possibilities, hence it is necessary to limit the design choices to only a limited fraction of feasible ones. This is done in the following section.

Diagram 3: Design Option Tree Part 1

Diagram 4: Design Option Tree Part 2

8.2. Concept Elimination

The next step in the process is to eliminate concepts which cannot be implemented in the design. The reasoning for eliminating these concepts can be divided into 3 different subcategories. The first category are so called non-concepts that were included into the tree for completeness, but have no real implementation. They are red in the tree. The second category are non-feasible concepts which violate the laws of physics or that are extremely impractical. They are marked by black crosses. Additionally, in this category concepts which are found to directly oppose requirements are also included. Finally, the third category includes concepts which cannot be analysed and developed yet (for which at the present moment there is no in-depth research, or that due to limited resources it cannot be feasible within the given schedule). They are marked with purple. In the following section we explain the reasoning behind elimination.

- **Wing Configuration:** Overall, there are not many concepts that can be immediately discarded from this tree. Balloons, flying engine and flying engine with wing are all non-feasible options within the required design. The balloon is slow and very sensitive to wind, and requires a considerable amount of space for take-off and landing. The flying engine is not comfortable for the passengers and will have sub optimal controllability. Finally, the options with more than 2 wings are also discarded. Even though analysis is possible it would be significantly more work and there is no evidence to suggest that it would show an important improvement in performance, hence it is not worth pursuing further.
- **Cruise Propulsion:** A lot of options can be eliminated from this sub-tree. Rocket engines, magnetic lift, solar sail, ion propulsion, ionising air, flapping wing and kite are all non-feasible concepts for our aircraft. Although these options exist and are used in different vehicles, none of them can be implemented into the mission of the eVTOL in a practical manner.
- **Energy:** Using lasers for energy transfer, a flywheel, wind energy and human power are all non-feasible concepts. Non rechargeable batteries, fossil fuels, bio-fuel, nuclear energy and heat based energy are also non-feasible for our design. A lot of these options are not sustainable, as they are polluting and/or dangerous, and thus cannot be implemented. Heat based is extremely impractical and nuclear energy is dangerous. Hydrogen combustion cannot be analysed and developed by us. Current technologies generate too much NO_x gas to be used in a city environment.
- **Control:** In this sub-tree a number of concepts are also discarded. Separate rotating thrusters for control, thrusters, shift of c.g. through moving passenger and reaction wheel are non-feasible and also some of these options oppose the non-polluting requirement. These options are usually implemented for spacecraft and not aircraft due to low gravitational forces. The shift of the cabin is also non-feasible. It is very difficult to design and over-complicated. The shift in batteries still has not been developed yet. Although this would theoretically work, it would be complicated to include, and would not necessarily improve performance. A larger fuselage or wing would be needed to make space for the shifting
- **Moving on the ground:** A number of concepts are removed due to limitations resulting from the requirements. Options including pushing and non-ability to move on ground are feasible concepts, however they violate the moving-on-ground requirement without external aid. Having to push the eVTOL was considered impractical, and having no ability to move on ground is sub-optimal for ground operations.
- **Cabin configuration:** A number of options are eliminated from this sub-tree. 1 + 1x4 (sideways) is a non-feasible and was not developed yet. These concepts are included for completeness, this configuration is very inefficient in terms of drag and weight reduction or even comfort. Having a configuration without cockpit and alternating formation with cockpit is non-feasible. It is decided that having a cockpit is necessary, as the pilot will have a better working experience and will not be distracted by the passengers. The alternating formation is judged to be too uncomfortable for moving within the fuselage.
- **Take-off:** Two high level concepts are immediately discarded. Aerostatic and mechanical take-off are non-feasible concepts. Both options provide non-optimal and extremely slow solutions for take-off, which would violate the endurance requirement.

- Take off to cruise transition: Only a few concepts are discarded, as most of them can result in efficient solutions. Vertical orientation in take-off and horizontal orientation in cruise are non-feasible concepts. The first aspect is non-feasible as no chemical propulsion is allowed in order to limit the production of polluting substances to zero. The second concept is non-feasible due to the large amount of drag experienced by the aircraft when in cruise and also shows significant difficulty for control. Additionally, dropping dedicated engines after take-off are non-feasible and cannot be analysed within the given schedule. By using this method, the weight of the engines used for take-off would be eliminated during cruise, however, the operations and vehicles needed, result in the option being over-complicated to be developed further in the design process. This is due to the fact that little or no research is present at the moment and hence would lead to high scheduling problems.

There are other concepts which are not eliminated in the previous process but are also not included in the concepts presented in section 8.3. The reason for this is that the team quickly identified that these concepts did not have any clear advantages over the other options but can not be eliminated using the criteria used to eliminate the concepts previously discarded. An example of this is the ducted engine option. This option is seen as being a more complex and inefficient version of using thrust vectoring by rotating the engines and thus was not included in any concepts. Also the fact that no current eVTOL concepts use this solution is also a proof that it is not an efficient solution. Furthermore, ducted engines are usually used for aircraft with one powerful jet engine. The same reasoning can be applied to thrust vectoring through outlet direction manipulation.

8.3. Elimination Process

The design option tree yields several options per system, which have to be combined to get a total conceptual design for the aircraft. In this section, 15 designs are first discussed, and then an elimination process is done to end up with 3 designs that are to be analysed in the midterm report.

8.3.1. Overview of Conceptual Designs

This subsection will discuss the different designs that came from the design option trees and the reasoning behind them. The designs are based on several of the parameters in the design option trees, which are wing configuration, control method and the propulsion system, which consists of a take-off system and a cruise system. The transition system from take-off to cruise was also considered.

The first concept is a tandem aircraft with different wing sizes, as shown in Figure 8.1. It features a distributed propulsion system. It is controlled by thrust vectoring and the transition from take-off to cruise is done by rotating the distributed propulsion system. This design is inspired by the Lilium Jet¹ and the Airbus Vahana².

Concept 2, see Figure 8.2, does not have wings but is instead lifted purely by the four propellers mounted to the fuselage. These propellers can change orientation, and can rotate to change the direction in which the aircraft is flying, which is also how the transition from take-off to cruise takes place. The control of the aircraft is done by thrust vectoring and differential thrust.

¹lilium.com/jet

²airbus.com/innovation/zero-emission/urban-air-mobility/vahana.html

Figure 8.1: Design 1: Tandem aircraft with distributed propulsion system.

Figure 8.2: Design 2: Quadcopter with rotating propellers

The third concept is a conventional wing configuration, with a single wing and an empennage, as shown in Figure 8.3. Electric fans power the aircraft in cruise, and dedicated engines are included in the wings for take-off. The transition between them is done by activating the electric fans when a sufficient altitude is reached, and gradually reducing the power on the take-off engines as more lift is generated by the wings.

The fourth concept's appearance is inspired by a drone, where the mounting beams of the drone are replaced by wings. It features two slightly swept wings in a tandem configuration with tiltable propeller electric engines at the tips of each wing, which can be seen in Figure 8.4. This configuration allows for lift generation by wings during cruise, making horizontal flight consume less power than design 2. Control is achieved by control surfaces in cruise and differential thrust for take off and landing. The vertical tail and rudder are still to be discussed, because lateral control in cruise could also be maintained by differential thrust and the vertical tail creates extra drag in cruise. However, in case of engine failure or energy loss, the vertical tail could be beneficial by allowing the pilot to control and land the aircraft in gliding flight. A different emergency solution with a smaller effect on drag might be possible, like spoilers close to wingtips that create extra drag and yaw the plane into the turn.

Figure 8.3: Design 3: Conventional aircraft with dedicated take-off system

Figure 8.4: Design 4: Quadcopter with wings

The fifth concept, see Figure 8.5, is a flying wing with the cockpit attached from the bottom, 2 large tiltable propellers at wingtips and a helicopter-like tail to provide stability in vertical flight. Solar panels are placed on the large surface of the wing to increase range on sunny days.

Concept 6 was originally based on the Dornier 335, which is a WWII plane with one pushing propeller at the back and one pulling propeller in the nose. The idea was for the 2 propellers to rotate upwards or downwards or a combination of those during vertical flight. The final concept shown here has a redesigned fuselage to create more space for passengers. Cruise control is achieved by the original plane's control surfaces. During take off, longitudinal control is managed by differential thrust, but longitudinal control is more difficult, as there are only 2 propellers. One solution is to have the

downwards facing vertical stabiliser act as a thrust-vectoring flap (the whole vertical tail rotates about its horizontal axis). Another force affecting the longitudinal stability is the relative speed and pitch of the counter rotating propellers. A combination of the propellers and the thrust vectoring flap could be enough to stabilise the vertical flight, although that would be very difficult to design correctly.

Figure 8.5: Design 5: Flying wing with solar panels

Figure 8.6: Design 6: Conventional aircraft with front and rear mounted rotating engines.

Concept 7 has a conventional airplane configuration with electric propulsion distributed on the insides of the wing and horizontal stabiliser, which both rotate to a vertical position for take off and landing. For additional control during cruise there is a V-tail in the aft section. The engines inside the wing allow for an alternative box-wing configuration with increased engine size. Alternatively, a biplane could be used with engines mounted in between.

Concept 8 is a flying wing with propulsion distributed along the trailing edge of the wing, and more propellers, which can be either distributed or just a number of bigger one, on the leading edge. The trailing edge propulsion would be positioned on a flap that can deflect downward and the propellers on the leading edge can be moved upwards. A small vertical tail is also included for lateral stability; furthermore, a vertical propeller is placed for control.

Figure 8.7: Design 7: Engines mounted inside the wing

Figure 8.8: Design 8: Flying wing distributed propulsion

The ninth concept consists of a tandem wing configuration. It has 4 embedded engines only for take-off, and 4 other engines which can rotate. The aircraft uses thrust vectoring for control and a conceptual drawing is shown in figure 8.9.

Concept 10 uses a box wing configuration combined with distributed propulsion along the wings. For the take-off to cruise transition all the engines can rotate and for control the aircraft relies on thrust

vectoring combined with a vertical tail for stability.

Figure 8.9: Design 9: Canard with distributed prop and rotating propellers.

Figure 8.10: Design 10: Box wing with distributed propulsion.

Concept 11 is a canard aircraft presented in figure 8.11. It uses a distributed propulsion system and rotates the entire wing in order to achieve vertical take-off and landing. For control it relies on aerodynamic control surfaces including ailerons and rudder.

Concept 12 uses a double fuselage, as can be seen in figure 8.12. This design produces most of its lift using the wing that connects the two fuselages. On this wing, a propeller is placed to provide lift during take-off. Two smaller wings are placed on the external sides of the fuselages to attach the rotating engines which work during take-off and cruise. A horizontal tail with an elevator and two vertical tails connecting the fuselages are added for stability, control and structural rigidity.

Figure 8.11: Design 11: Canard with distributed prop and rotating wing.

Figure 8.12: Design 12: Double fuselage design.

The 13th concept is an aircraft with a conventional configuration, a tail for control and stability and a main wing for the generation of lift. It is shown in figure 8.13. The take-off to cruise transition is done by rotating the engines, which are electric propellers.

Concept 14 is a single wing airplane with two fixed rotors in the wing, 2 rotating fans in the back and 2 of them in the front. All 6 rotors are used for vertical flight, but for cruise the holes in the wing close and only the 4 tiltable rotors provide forward thrust. Stability is achieved by the ring wing around the back engine and control is provided by ailerons and small movable flaps on the aft part of the aft engines for thrust vectoring.

Figure 8.13: Design 13: A conventional aircraft with multiple propellers.

Figure 8.14: Design 14: Single wing aircraft with 6 engines, 4 rotating.

The final design is shown in Figure 8.15. It is a flying wing with a central fuselage. There are 4 propellers used exclusively for take-off, and a single engine on the rear of the plane used for cruise. The plane also features control surfaces on the wings for control during cruise, and will also have differential thrust.

Figure 8.15: Design 15: Flying wing with single engine for cruise and 4 engines for take-off.

8.3.2. Concept Selection

This list of designs needs to be reduced to three final designs. The first step for this was to eliminate the concepts with the most significant weaknesses. The eliminated concepts, along with the reason for their elimination, are presented in the list below:

- **Concept 2:** Concept 2 was discarded because it has no wing(s), meaning that it relies completely on the propulsion system to produce both thrust and lift for the entirety of the mission. Considering the range of 300 km required for the mission, this is very inefficient and perhaps not even feasible using electric propulsion.
- **Concept 5:** This concept features a flying wing design with separately tilting engines. When tilting only the engines, a very unfavourable downwash is created on the wings, which is bad for performance. For most of the designs, the entire wing tilts to avoid this. This is not an option for concept 5, since it is a flying wing and tilting the entire aircraft would be very uncomfortable for passengers. The design is also unsafe when one of the two engines fails.
- **Concept 6:** This design has bad controllability and problematic lateral stability during take-off, and is also a dangerous configuration in case one of the engines fails. Therefore it is eliminated.
- **Concept 8:** The main difference between this design and concept 5 is the engine placement and number of engines. This design has the same problem with the negative effect of the downwash by tilting only the rotors, and not the entire wing.
- **Concept 11:** This concept features a canard configuration. The entire wing rotates for vertical take-off and landing. Controlling the aircraft is done with dedicated ailerons and flaps. This is

inefficient as you add systems to the aircraft which are not needed since control can also be achieved with thrust vectoring, which is possible due to the rotating wings.

- **Concept 12:** This design was considered unnecessarily complicated and inconvenient. Having two fuselages divides the passengers in two groups which will mean the passengers will not be able to talk to each other directly. The double fuselage will also reduce the lifting surface to wet surface area ratio, which is not good for the lift-to-drag ratio, and is heavier than a single fuselage version.

The final three concepts were selected through group voting, where all group members gave their opinion on which initial designs have the highest development potential. This was done by both considering technical performance, thinking about originality of the design and, of course, taking into account personal preference.

The first concept chosen is a **combination of concepts 1 and 4**. The tandem wing configuration has been proven to work well for vertical take-off and landing. The transition from vertical to horizontal flight can be done by rotating the engines or wings. The addition of wings is favourable for the cruise phase, as these generate lift much more efficiently than with the use of engines. This means that the engines are used primarily to provide forward thrust and are not necessary for generation of vertical force during cruise.

The second selected concept is **concept 10**, which is a Prandtl boxed wing version of concept 1, which also uses ducted fans instead of open propellers. In this design, the jets are fixed to flaps, which rotate downwards for vertical flight. The use of more and smaller engines can provide an increase in efficiency and redundancy, which consequently increase the performance and safety of the aircraft. The use of the Prandtl boxed wing provides an increase in aerodynamic efficiency through a reduction in lift losses due to wingtip vortices and a reduction in induced drag due to the higher effective aspect ratio.

The last concept to further analyse is **concept 14**. It features dedicated two engines for take-off and landing, which makes it different from the other two concepts. Having dedicated engines for vertical flight could be beneficial, because cruise requires less thrust than take-off. When only 4 of the 6 engines rotate for cruise, structural weight can be reduced while still satisfying the cruise thrust requirement. It will be interesting to compare this design to the others that rotate the entire propulsion system, in order to see which configuration is superior during trade-off.

This paragraph gives the reasons for not selecting the remaining concepts. Concept 3 has a conventional configuration, but without rotating engines the propulsive system is over designed since the aircraft is then not operating at maximum power during take-off, when the most power is required. Concept 7 will have very ineffective wings because the airfoil shape is heavily compromised by the engines inside the wings. This can be compensated by using a bit of the thrust for an upwards force, but this is inefficient and requires more energy than using aerodynamic lift. Design 9 has rotating engines but not the wing, causing an unfavourable downwash on the wing itself. The design is still possible, but inefficient and therefore not further pursued. Concept 13 has quite a conventional configuration, but both the wings and therefore the engines are behind the centre of gravity. This makes the aircraft hard to control in take-off and landing, and means that the rear-engines will have to generate downward thrust which is highly inefficient. Concept 15 will be very ineffective for cruise when the rear engine fails, since the other engines are dedicated to take-off only. Controlling the pitch of the aircraft will also be hard since all the take-off engines are close to the center of gravity and thus have small moment arms.

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